

Diffusive escape from an entropic metastable state[†]

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Abstract : We consider a system of Brownian particles confined in a two-dimensional symmetric tri-lobal enclosure. By employing two external noise forces of different kind, one additive and another multiplicative along x -direction, we demonstrate that a correlation between two external noise processes driving the thermally activated particles in this symmetric tri-lobal confinement may cause a symmetry breaking entropic stability and a difference in relative stability of the two side-lobes with respect to the middle lobe. This leads to an asymmetric localization of population and splitting of escape rate from the middle lobe to the other lobes.

Keywords : Brownian motion, confinement of particles, entropic potential.

I. Introduction

The problem of stochastic motion of overdamped Brownian particles through a narrow tube of varying cross-section is an interesting area of research in recent times¹⁻³. A key point in understanding the nature of problem is that the boundary effects play a nontrivial role for the system as the unevenness of the confinement gives rise to an effective entropic potential when the higher dimensional problem is mapped into lower dimension^{2,3}. A popular scheme of this approximate description in reduced dimension is the Fick-Jacob equation¹ where the diffusion coefficient becomes spatially inhomogeneous. The concept of entropic potential has been extensively used over the last several years in a number of issues related to constrained motion of particles in periodic channels⁴⁻¹⁵. The entropic analogs of a few stochastic phenomena like stochastic resonance⁷, resonant activation¹¹, particle mobility¹³, noise-induced non-equilibrium transition¹⁵ etc. have been explored recently. This development is particularly important for understanding geometry-controlled chemical kinetics¹⁶⁻¹⁸, polymer transition through a hole¹⁹⁻²¹, narrow escape problem for diffusive motion of ions and molecules in confined biological microdomains¹⁶.

The essential physics of confinement in the aforesaid cases relies on symmetric bilobal confinement as a model enclosure. Here we concentrate on the motion of Brownian particles confined in the middle lobe of a symmetric tri-lobal enclosure. In the absence of any bias force the particles diffuse only by thermal fluctuations resulting in equalization of population density in the two side-lobes. Introduction of an additive white noise also cannot lead to any change of time averaged relative population density of the two side lobes. The situation remains same even if, in addition, one introduces a multiplicative white noise which makes the diffusion state-dependent²². The aim of the present work is to look for a scheme which leads to a symmetry breaking resulting in a preferential population distribution in one of the two side-lobes. We show that the presence of correlation between the applied additive and multiplicative noises may cause a change in the relative stability of the side-lobes with respect to the middle one. This correlation-induced interference of the two noises leads to a splitting of rate of escape from the central lobe to others. The correlation between noise processes has been the subject of study in a number of issues. For example, it has been shown that correlation strongly influences the noise-induced transitions from

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unimodal to bimodal distribution. Our proposal in this work concentrates on altering the relative stability of the two side-lobes with respect to the middle one of a tri-lobal confinement under the influence of correlation between the noises, where the underlying idea rests on controlling the escape rates from middle to the others.

The paper is organized as follows : In Section II we discuss the model for overdamped Brownian motion of a particle subjected to a white multiplicative noise and a white additive noise in a symmetric tri-lobal two-dimensional confined space. The later half of this section is devoted to the derivation of the Fokker-Planck description in reduced dimension. In Section III, we explore the phenomenon of noise correlation-induced splitting of escape rate and asymmetric localization of the particle in a stationary state in terms of the shape of the stationary probability distribution function. The paper is concluded in Section IV.

II. The model, entropic potential, and Fokker-Planck description

(A) The model

Consider an overdamped Brownian particle in a two-dimensional symmetrical tri-lobal enclosure subjected to a constant bias force G acting along the transverse y -direction, kept in a thermostat at a temperature T and subjected to two stochastic forces $\xi_1(t)$ and $\xi_2(t)$ along the x -direction. The governing Langevin equation is :

$$\gamma \frac{dr}{dt} = -Ge_y + \xi_1(t)e_x + x\xi_2(t)e_x + \eta(t) \quad (1)$$

where ‘ γ ’ denotes the dissipation constant and ‘ r ’ is the position vector of the particle in Cartesian space and e_y and e_x are the unit vectors along y and x direction, respectively. $\xi_i(t)$ and $\eta(t)$ are white Gaussian noises with the following properties :

$$\langle \xi_i(t) \rangle = 0; \langle \eta_i(t) \rangle = 0 \quad (2)$$

and

$$\langle \eta_i(t)\eta_j(t') \rangle = 2\gamma kT\delta_{ij}\delta(t-t'),$$

where $i, j = x, y$

$$\langle \xi_i(t)\xi_j(t') \rangle = 2Q_i\delta_{ij}\delta(t-t'), \text{ where } i, j = 1, 2 \quad (3)$$

The cross correlation of $\xi_i(t)$'s is defined as :

$$\langle \xi_1(t)\xi_2(t') \rangle = \langle \xi_2(t)\xi_1(t') \rangle = 2\lambda\sqrt{Q_1Q_2}\delta(t-t') \quad (4)$$

and thermal noise and external noise processes are uncorrelated

$$\langle \xi_i(t)\eta_j(t') \rangle = 0 \quad (5)$$

In presence of confinement, the reflecting boundary walls of the enclosure is defined by the following functions

$$\omega_l(x) = -\omega_u(x) = L_y(x/L_x)^6 - 2.0 L_y(x/L_x)^4 + 10 L_y(x/L_x)^2 - \frac{b}{2} \quad (6)$$

where ω_u and ω_l correspond to the lower and upper boundary functions respectively. The characteristic length L_x refers to the distance between any one of the bottleneck position and the position of the nearest maximal width. L_y corresponds to the narrowing of the bottleneck functions and ‘ b ’ refers to the remaining width of the bottleneck. The local half-width of the system is defined as -

$$\omega(x) = \frac{\omega_u(x) - \omega_l(x)}{2} \quad (7)$$

This particular choice of confinement is intended to resemble the classical setup for the symmetric triple well energy barrier. In the limit of very large G , the particle is in practice restricted to explore the region very close to the lower boundary of the enclosure, recovering the effect of an energetic triple well potential.

Now to make the description dimensionless we scale all the units in the unit of L_x i.e. $\tilde{X} = x/L_x$, $\tilde{Y} = y/L_x$, $\tilde{b} = b/L_x$, $-\tilde{\omega}_u(x) = \tilde{\omega}_l(x) = \tilde{\omega}_l/L_x$. We scale temperature by $\tilde{T} = T/T_R$ where T_R is the reference temperature and the time in units $\tilde{t} = t/\tau$ and $\tilde{G} = G/F_R$ where $F_R = \gamma L_x/\tau$ and $\tau = \gamma L_x^2/(k_B T_R)$, i.e. twice the particle takes to diffuse through a distance L_x at a temperature T_R . For simplicity we shall now omit symbols for the rest of our treatment.

In dimensionless form the Langevin equation (1) and the boundary function (6) read as -

$$\frac{\partial x}{\partial t} = \sqrt{Q_1}\xi(t) + \sqrt{Q_2}x\xi_2(t) + \sqrt{D}\eta_x(t)$$

$$\frac{\partial y}{\partial t} = -G + \sqrt{D}\eta_y(t) \quad (8)$$

and

$$\omega_l(x) = -\omega_u(x) = 0.01\epsilon x^6 - 0.2\epsilon x^4 + \epsilon x^2 - \frac{b}{2} \quad (9)$$

where we define an aspect ratio $\varepsilon = L_y/L_x$ and the noise strengths are scaled by T as $D = T/T_R$ and $Q_i = Q_i/TR$ ($i = 1, 2$).

Now the Langevin process (8) can be described by the following 2D Fokker-Planck equation²³ -

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} P(x, y, t) = & -\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \{ \chi(x) P(x, y, t) \} \\ & + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \{ (\varphi(x) P(x, y, t)) \} \\ & + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(G + D \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right) P(x, y, t) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

We impose the reflecting boundary condition on $P(x, y, t)$, the probability distribution function of finding the particle at (x, y) at time t and furthermore we have

$$\chi(x) = Q_2 x + \lambda(Q_1 Q_2)^{1/2}$$

and

$$\varphi(x) = Q_2 x^2 + 2\lambda \sqrt{Q_1 Q_2} x + Q_1 + D \quad (11)$$

Now let us define a dimensionless potential function $\psi(x, y)$ as :

$$\psi(x, y) = \ln(\varphi(x)) - \int_0^x \frac{\chi(x')}{\varphi(x')} dx' + \int_0^y \frac{G}{D} dy' \quad (12)$$

The Fokker-Planck equation can then be alternatively expressed by the following Smoluchowski form -

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} P(x, y, t) = & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \varphi(x) e^{-\psi(x, y)} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} e^{\psi(x, y)} \\ & P(x, y, t) + D \frac{\partial}{\partial y} e^{-\psi(x, y)} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} e^{\psi(x, y)} P(x, y, t) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

(B) Reduction of dimensionality of the Fokker-Planck equation

Since the Fokker-Planck dynamics given by eq. (13) with the boundary condition (9) can not be solved analytically we reduce the dimensionality of the problem by assuming a fast equilibrium along the y -direction²⁻¹². To do so, let us introduce the marginal probability density along x , $P(x, t)$ which is obtained by integrating $P(x, y, t)$ over the transverse y -direction

$$P(x, t) = \int P(x, y, t) dy \quad (14)$$

From eqs. (13) and (14) we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} P(x, t) = & \\ & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int \varphi(x) e^{-\psi(x, y)} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} e^{\psi(x, y)} P(x, y, t) dy \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Assuming a local equilibrium in the y -direction and an x -dependent potential function $A(x)$ which is defined as -

$$e^{-A(x)/D} = \int e^{-\psi(x, y)} dy \quad (16)$$

one may define a conditional local equilibrium distribution of ' y ' at a given x as $\rho(y, x)$. Here $\rho(y, x)$ is normalized for ' x '. By definition

$$\int \rho(y, x) dy = 1 \quad (17)$$

Now, we express the two-dimensional probability distribution approximated by -

$$P(x, y, t) = \rho(y, x) P(x, t) \quad (18)$$

Finally we can find out the equation for the marginal probability using eq. (14) and eq. (18). The equation for the marginal probability is -

$$\frac{\partial P(x, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \varphi(x) e^{-A(x)/D} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} e^{A(x)/D} P(x, t) \quad (19)$$

This is the Smoluchowski equation in a quasi-one dimensional form. Now we can express $A(x)$ as (from eq. (16))

$$\begin{aligned} A(x) = & (D/2) \ln [Q_2 x^2 + \\ & 2\lambda \sqrt{Q_1 Q_2} x + Q_1 + D] - \\ & D \ln \left(\frac{2D}{G} \sinh \frac{G\omega(x)}{D} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The potential $A(x)$ was not present in the 2D Langevin description, but in the quasi 1D form of the Fokker-Planck equation. This arises due to entropic restrictions associated with the shape of the enclosure. So, eq. (19) describes the motion of the Brownian particle in the entropic potential. The potential $A(x)$ is determined by several quantities G , D , Q_1 , Q_2 and λ . For a structure of the enclosure shown in Fig. 1(a) the entropic potential takes the form of a symmetric triple well as was shown in Fig. 1(b). As the width of the enclosure approaches to zero, the potential $A(x)$ diverges. We now consider two limiting situations depending on the relative values of the transverse force G , thermal energy D and local half-width of the system $\omega(x)$.

Fig. 1(a). A schematic plot of the two-dimensional space of the particle with model structure parameters.

Fig. 1(b). A plot of spatial variation of the effective potential $A(x)$ in 1D for the same system as depicted in Fig. 1(a) for the parameter set : $b = 3.2$, $G = 0.001$ and $D = 0.25$.

Energy dominated situation : When $\frac{G\omega(x)}{D} \gg 1$ eq.

relevant constant. This is the energy dominated situation.

(20) yields $A(x) = \frac{D}{2} \ln(\varphi(x)) - G\omega(x)$, neglecting ir-

Entropy dominated situation : When $\frac{G\omega(x)}{D} \ll 1$ eq.

(20) yields $A(x) = \frac{D}{2} \ln(\varphi(x)) - D \ln(2\omega(x))$, which is independent of ' G '. Here, the effective potential is entirely dominated by the purely entropic contribution through the width function of the enclosure. Now we shall study the relative escape rates from the middle lobe of the effective potential (x_0) to the middle lobe of both the terminal lobe of the entropic potential. It is obvious when no random forces with the strengths Q_1 and Q_2 are present in the system the right hand side escape rate (R_r)(x_0 to x_m) and left hand side escape rate (R_l)(x_0 to $-x_m$) are equal due to symmetric triple well nature of the effective potential (i.e. (R_l/R_r)-transition rate ratio $T(\lambda)$ is unity for all D). Now we shall explore the effect of the external zero mean random forces and their correlation on the transition rate ratio $T(\lambda)$.

III. Results and discussions

(A) Mean first passage time

First we shall adopt the Mean First Passage Time (MFPT) approach to study the variation of $T(\lambda)$ in presence of non-zero Q_1 , Q_2 and λ value. The transition rate of the particle from x_0 to $\pm x_m$ can be calculated as the inverse of the MFPT required by the particle to move from x_0 to $\pm x_m$ for a particular value of D respectively. This implies that we may define the transition rate by R_l

$= 1/\tau(x_0 \rightarrow -x_m)$ and $R_r = 1/\tau(x_0 \rightarrow x_m)$. Consequently we have

$$T(\lambda) = \tau(x_0 \rightarrow +x_m)/\tau(x_0 \rightarrow -x_m) \quad (21)$$

For the present potential $A(x)$, $\tau(x_0 \rightarrow x_i)$ can be calculated using the definition of MFPT as -

$$\tau(x_0 \rightarrow x_m) = \frac{1}{D} \int_{x_0}^{+x_m} e^{A(x')/D} dx' \int_{-x_r}^{x'} e^{-A(x'')/D} dx''$$

$$\tau(x_0 \rightarrow -x_m) = \frac{1}{D} \int_{x_0}^{-x_m} e^{A(x')/D} dx' \int_{x_r}^{x'} e^{-A(x'')/D} dx'' \quad (22)$$

where $\pm x_r$ reflecting boundaries for the present problem. Since $A(x)$ is an asymmetric function, $\tau(x_0 \rightarrow -x_m)$ and $\tau(x_0 \rightarrow x_m)$ are not the same for a nonzero λ (also when both Q_1 and Q_2 nonzero). It is thus apparent from the above expression that the transition rate from the middle lobe to the terminal lobes splits up due to the interplay of two correlated stochastic external forces. The ratio of the transition rates deviates from unity ($T(\lambda) \neq 1$) only when the two external drives are correlated ($\lambda \neq 0$). If $\lambda = 0$, $A(x)$ is a symmetric function of x and the ratio of the transition rates becomes unity ($T(\lambda = 0) = 1$). In Fig. 2(a) we have plotted the variation of $T(\lambda)$ vs G for several

Fig. 2(a). Plot of the ratio of the transition rate ($T(\lambda)$) versus G for the parameter set : $G = 0.001$, $Q_1 = 0.5$, $Q_2 = 0.5$, $b = 3.2$ and $D = 0.22$.

values of λ . The variations depict that $T(\lambda) \neq 1$ for entire range of G which shows that splitting of escape rate occurs for both entropy-dominated and energy-dominated regions. It is also apparent that the ratio of escape rate exhibits a crossover from entropy-dominated regime to energy-dominated regime with the increase of G . The extent of dominance of either zone and the range of crossover regime are significantly influenced by λ . A lower λ makes the crossover zone smaller. In Fig. 2(b) we present the variation of the ratio of the transition rates ($T(\lambda)$) as a function of scaled temperature for several values of the

to the fact that with the increase of intensities of the external noise the synchronization probability of the noise realizations from two noise processes [$\xi_1(t)$, $\xi_2(t)$] in a given time increases as a result of which the transition probability to the right increases. A high value of noise intensities results in randomization in the system.

(B) Stationary solution

Eq. (19) can be expressed as a continuity equation - $\partial P(x, t)/\partial t = -(\partial/\partial x)(J(x, t))$ where $J(x, t)$ is given by

$$J(x, t) = -\varphi(x) \frac{1}{D} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} A(x) P(x, t) - \varphi(x) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} P(x, t).$$

Fig. 2(b). Ratio of transition rates ($T(\lambda)$) versus scaled temperature (D) plot for several values of coupling strength and for the parameter set $G = 0.001$, $Q_2 = 0.05$, $Q_1 = 0.5$ and $b = 3.2$.

coupling strength (λ). It is also apparent that the ratio of the transition rates at a very low scaled temperature (D) significantly differs from unity and tends to equalize in the high temperature limit. For a fixed temperature the ratio of the transition rates deviates more from unity for an increase of the coupling strength (λ).

In Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) we plot the ratio of the transition rates as a function of the intensities (Q_1 , Q_2) of the external noises, respectively. One observes that with the increase of intensities of the external noises the magnitude of ($T(\lambda)$) increases to a maximum followed by a decrease. This resonance-like behavior is observed due

Now for the equilibrium state $J(x, t) = 0$, the solution of probability distribution function becomes

$$P_S(x) = N\varphi(x)^2 \frac{2D}{G} \sinh\left(\frac{G\omega(x)}{D}\right) \tag{23}$$

where the normalization constant 'N' is expressed as

$$N^{-1} = \int_{-x_r}^{x_r} \frac{2D}{G} \frac{\sinh\left(\frac{G\omega(x')}{D}\right)}{\varphi(x')^2} dx' \tag{24}$$

and subscript in P_S denotes the steady state nature of the

Fig. 3(a). Variation of the ratio of the transition rate ($T(\lambda)$) as function of the strength of additive noise and for several values of coupling strength and for the parameter set : $D = 0.25$, $G = 0.001$, $Q_2 = 0.05$ and $b = 3.2$.

Fig. 3(b). Variation of the ratio of the transition rate ($T(\lambda)$) as function of the strength of multiplicative noise for the same parameter set as Fig. 2(b) but for $Q_1 = 0.5$.

solution. Again in the entropic limit, i.e. when $(G\omega(x)/D) \ll 1$, the $P_S(x)$ and ' N ' becomes

$$P_S(x) = 2N\varphi(x)^{\frac{1}{2}}\omega(x) \text{ and } N^{-1} = \int_{-x_r}^{x_r} \frac{2\omega(x)}{\sqrt{\varphi(x')}} dx'.$$

It is apparent from expressions (23, 24) that as a result of interplay of two stochastic driving forces the distribution function are asymmetric in space. The asymmetry in the distribution function arises due to asymmetric diffusion of the particles. To illustrate the asymmetric localization of the particles we have plotted the distribution function as a function of position in Fig. 4(a) which shows a symmetric distribution in the absence of the external driving forces. The same plot in the presence of additive and multiplicative noises but for no cross correlation ($\lambda = 0$) is also a symmetric distribution although the magnitude of the maximal position has been changed

lobe which diffuse to the terminal lobes at a relatively slower rate and the particles spend most of the time in the middle lobe. This implies that higher strength of forcing destabilizes the side lobes compared to the middle lobe. When the two stochastic forces are correlated ($\lambda \neq 0$), interestingly, because of the spatial asymmetry in effective potential, the Brownian particles are preferentially localized in the left lobe compared to the right.

(C) Asymmetric localization

To proceed further we require a quantifier which measures the asymmetry in localization in the two side lobes. To this end we choose the mean position of the particle as its measure. For a symmetric distribution mean position $\langle x \rangle = 0$ and for the localization of the particles in the left or right lobe, the value of mean position is negative or positive, respectively. Thus an expression for $\langle x \rangle$

Fig. 4(a). Stationary probability distribution function $P(x)$ vs position x plot depicting the changes of distribution due to the addition of external noises for the parameter set : $D = 0.25$, $b = 3.2$ and $G = 0.001$.

compared to that of the former. In this case the distribution function still remains symmetric but the population of the middle lobe is much higher than that of the side lobes due to the fact that in the presence of multiplicative noise the effective potential becomes asymmetric. As a result the particles in the side lobes diffuse to the middle more quickly as compared to the particles of the middle

from a direct steady state solution of Fokker-Planck equation (19) can be formally obtained as -

$$\langle x \rangle = \int_{-x_r}^{x_r} x' P(x') dx' \tag{25}$$

We now proceed to analyze the behavior of localization

Fig. 4(b). Variation of mean position $\langle x \rangle$ as a function of scaled temperature D for several values of coupling strength and for the parameter set : $G = 0.001$, $Q_1 = 1.0$, $Q_2 = 0.05$ and $b = 3.2$.

(mean position) with the variation of system parameters. In absence of any correlation of two external noise processes the variation of $\langle x \rangle$ with D is expected to show a null value for all D . For $\lambda \neq 0$, the departure of $\langle x \rangle$ from zero toward the negative direction indicates the preferential distribution of the product in the left lobe. The variation of mean position $\langle x \rangle$ as a function of temperature for several values of strength of correlation for the external forces as shown in Fig. 4(b) corroborates this assertion. Fig. 4(b) also reveals that for fixed values of temperature and other parameter sets the mean position increases with the decrease of the strength of cross correlation. It clearly indicates that, for an appropriate correlation between additive and multiplicative noises, the asymmetric localization of the particles is facilitated.

IV. Conclusion

We have considered the diffusive movement of the particles in a tri-lobal enclosure driven simultaneously by two cross-correlated white noise processes. It has been shown that depending on the correlation between the two noise sources, one multiplicative and another additive, the relative stability of the two side lobes with respect to

the middle one may differ significantly. This originates from an asymmetry in an effective entropic potential of the system in reduced dimension due to interference of the two noises. An offshoot of this symmetry breaking effect is the splitting of escape rate from the middle lobe to the side lobes. We believe that entropic potential may take its presence felt in more complicated and realistic models where the thermally activated particles are forced to undergo constrained motion through an enclosure of complex structure like cellular micro-domains¹⁶.

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